
Between Subversion and Contradiction: Rethinking Saul Bellow's Fiction Through Deconstructive Analysis

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ABSTRACT

This article critically examines the problem of meaning in Saul Bellow's writings by tracing how the writer's strategies of subversion and deconstruction, along with his unique perspective on madness, life, and the world, shape his fictional narratives. This study further explores how theoretical reflections on morality and humanism reveal their limits when analyzed within their historical, political, social, economic, and intellectual contexts. The primary aim was to overemphasize how Bellow has attempted to make sense and unity out of difference and contradiction. Drawing on critical theories from Derrida, Habermas, Hegel, and other contemporary thinkers, this article reassesses Bellow's strategies of subversion and deconstruction, arguing that personal and ideological imperatives deeply influence his fictional world. Moreover, this study interrogates the extent to which Bellow's engagement with philosophy and criticism reflects a broader crisis of meaning. The findings highlight Bellow's selective appropriation of literary and philosophical traditions, questioning the limitations of his engagement with poststructuralist and feminist thought, as his narratives oscillate between radical subversion and entrenched ideological stances. This study contends that Bellow's fiction represents an unfinished intellectual project—one that simultaneously critiques and perpetuates the contradictions of modernity.

KEYWORDS: Saul Bellow, Deconstruction, Ideology, Subversion, Meaning, Philosophy, Modernity, Postmodernism

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INTRODUCTION

Deconstruction, as posited by Jacques Derrida (2020), challenges the notion of fixed meanings and binary oppositions in texts, advocating for an examination of the inherent instabilities and contradictions within language itself. Saul Bellow, a Canadian American Nobel Laureate, is an eminent literary figure who explored the human condition, delving into the complexities of modern existence through narratives that intertwine in intellectual rigor with emotional depth (Kociatkiewicz, 2008). The development of the confessional discourse in his writings depends on the nature of corresponding cultural and narrative power relationships at both discursive and public levels. Bellow, therefore, succeeded in addressing the critical issues of mental and emotional uncertainties, the anxiety of the age, the alienation of the intellectuals, and the gloomier aspects of the postmodern era. Moreover, he explored the themes of self-devaluation, existential themes associated with the ambiguities of his heroes, the endless pursuit of meaning in life, and the deprivation of humanity of any hope (Marrouchi, 2023).

One of the central ideas explored in this current study is the problem of meaning in the context of deconstructionism, as seen in Saul Bellow's fictional world. Symmetrically echoing the Enlightenment and post-Enlightenment thought, Bellow, from "Dangling Man" (1944) to "Ravelstein" (2001), has portrayed the Western image in a state of crisis, where the subject is unable to settle his views on art and life in relation to the intellectual and philosophical context of the age. The novelist has sought to unify contradictory concepts, such as morality and amorality, madness and wisdom, knowledge and the crisis of knowledge, the Holocaust and "after politics," "after identity," and the culture of memory. Therefore, we implicitly concede that his intellectual maturity can only be understood within the scope of these paradoxical patterns.

However, this statement is problematic. This paper examines this maturity within a framework that spans the Enlightenment and post-Enlightenment premises of thought. Although the novelist has been ceaselessly striving to establish order and unity out of disorder and contradiction, one could easily notice striking inconsistencies in his reflection on art, life, and the world. This, indeed, might consist of inconsistent instances of the author's political, intellectual, and philosophical views, the effects of ideology,

whatever it might be, on his writings, the limits of the moral ethics which he wanted to achieve, the problems between originality and intertextuality, the overlaps between the historical and the fictional, the subjective and the objective, fact, and imagination, and eventually the strategies of parody and equivocation. The point the researcher hopes to clarify is not to accuse the novelist of self-contradiction, disorder, or misunderstanding, but rather to expose their fictional world and view of life to a critical analysis that re-evaluates them and relates them to the general cultural and intellectual ethos that helped produce them. Bellow could not have gone further in his subversive and deconstructive strategies, not because political and historical forces hampered him- although this was true to a certain extent- because of some internal flaws that the environment within which he lived had shaped in his psychology. Pointing at these inconsistent standpoints is fundamental to shedding light on philosophy and the philosopher's duty while tracing contradictory and irreconcilable literary, political, cultural, and intellectual concerns. In the following, I have attempted to pinpoint how the author develops his views, assuming that one cannot elaborate on the strategies of subversion and deconstruction without having a good understanding of philosophy. In line with this, the purpose will not only be to trace the author's philosophical views on a wide range of issues but also to assess them critically, highlighting their major weaknesses and fallacies. When I first began reflecting on the novelist's strategies of deconstruction and subversion, the fundamental aim was to highlight the way Bellow attempted to create sense and unity out of difference and contradiction. However, this unity becomes deeply influenced by certain ideological assumptions and personal ends worth investigating in detail.

BETWEEN SUBVERSION AND CONTRADICTION:

Can one regard Bellow's strategies of deconstruction as a reflection of a certain ideology? Can subversion and deconstruction escape the act of criticism itself? Could we offer a critical reading that addresses the author's moral norms, his techniques of (re)presenting (his) stories, his political attitudes, and his intellectual reflections? And, if so, what are we to conclude? Let me respond to these questions by referring to the following quotation, which, I see, shall govern the context of my research. In the preface to his *Phenomenology of Mind*, Hegel describes the way "the new age" opens itself to the future and gives rebirth to the renewal of the history of ideas. He advocates that:

It is surely not difficult to see our time is a birth and transition to a new period. The spirit has broken with what was hitherto the world of its existence and imagination and is about to submerge all this in the past; it is at work giving itself a new form [...] [F]rivolity as well as the boredom that open up in the establishment and the indeterminate apprehension of something unknown are the harbingers of a forthcoming change. This gradual crumbling [...] is interrupted by the break of day, that, like lightning, all at once reveals the edifice of the new world. (Hegel, 1966, p. 20)

Unfortunately, ideology and the totalitarian metaphysical concepts of logocentrism, reason, and morality have unexpectedly limited the 'daring' gestures of revolution and emancipation. Bellow, on the contrary, could not settle his ideas in a unified way; rather he showed a "double mindedness" (Keskes, 2000, p. 162) that brought together the personal ends with political facts and historical and cultural contexts. As a matter of fact, he initiated an unfinished project, to borrow the words of Habermas, of subversion that began by acknowledging the sublime ideals of modernity, then moved to reevaluate them, and ultimately ended up radically refuting them. 'The birth and the transition to new [ideas],' to cite Hegel, necessarily demands a revisionist strategy that epitomizes self-consciousness about time and history. What Colin Davis calls "the after after-postmodern norms of thought" (Davis, 2004, p. 20) or what Derrida and Habermas refer to as 'the unfinished project of enlightenment or deconstruction' is what Saul Bellow has been ceaselessly attempting to achieve both genealogically and archeologically.

Strikingly enough, when Bellow managed to sketch his subversion strategies, he surprisingly revealed numerous moments of weakness and inconsistent instances in his fictional world. In fact, this is not only related to his stylistic, linguistic, and fictional deviations but also to his views concerning politics, religion, morality, philosophy, Man, art, and life in general. In tune with this, one instance that needs to be mentioned is the author's ambiguous and contradictory attitudes towards the Jewish and the Arab conflicts over the land of Palestine (?) Israel. Although the issue has overtones of a political nature, it also reduces humanitarian, moral, historical, and even religious connotations. Another instance that might be introduced is the author's 'odd' views on concepts such as morality, humanism, madness, wisdom, and intellectualism. In this respect, the oddity of these views stems from:

- a) Their lack of consistency and coherence,
- b) Their being too utopian and
- c) Sometimes, their being absurd.

Although the reader manages to understand them within the context of subversion and deconstruction, one cannot find logic and unity, nor can one be convinced of the illogical logic or random unity that seems to govern the author's world. Eventually, one can evoke the example of the overlap of discourses inherent in the Bellowian text, which traces not only the inconsistency in the way of writing but also in the final ends gathered from these texts. The combination of philosophical logic, the metaphorical and imaginative aspects of literature, historical facts, tactics, and political calculations makes the reader's duty a daunting task. The author's satirical gestures, his personal ends, and the limits of his theories of morality and humanism further aggravate the difficulty of coming out

with a coherent vision of the fictional world of the author.

His ideology and views concerning philosophy, politics, literary theory, and criticism played a vital role in shaping these inconsistencies and weaknesses. In this view, the Jewish ideological stances have unfathomably formulated the author's political and moral views. In more than one stance in either his interviews or even his writings, he deliberately advocated amoral and radical, if not 'Zionist attitudes' towards the Palestinians and the Arabs in general. While he acknowledged the rights of life, happiness, prosperity, freedom, and justice to his Jewish community in particular and the Western communities in general in the name of humanism and morality, he paradoxically deprived the same rights of the Palestinians. He publicly supported all the wars of the Jews against the Arabs and vehemently encouraged the expansion of the 'mythical and big state of Israel.' Ironically enough, his hilarious and shining slogans of happiness, freedom, justice, and morality turn out to be simple verbiage, totalitarian, and illusive concepts to cite Lyotard and Derrida. Concerning philosophy and literary theories and criticism, one can easily assert that although Bellow has managed to exploit their insights, he sometimes remained blind to the details of some theories; others were misunderstood and therefore misused by him, and others he was not aware of. For example, he showed a surprising ignorance of the post-war French theories of absurdity, existentialism, and surrealism. To this, he was also blind to the insights of the poststructuralist and after-poststructuralist theories of texts. Despite his long career as a writer, Bellow limited his focus to certain classical figures and trends of thought, a gesture that may possibly explain some of his totalitarian and extremist views. More strikingly, what the author referred to as the overlap between discourses- literary, religious, philosophical, political, and historical- though largely regarded as a significant and innovative stance in the process of storytelling, aggravates the unfamiliarity of his texts to the ordinary reader and further complicates the understanding of his personal ends behind the use of this technique. In short, the author seemed to be writing his books, putting them in the hands of his readers without being aware of the rapidly developing theories of criticism and philosophy.

Critics such as Daniel Fuchs and Harold Bloom have interestingly discussed the extent to which certain novelists and literary trends have influenced Saul Bellow. Fuchs, for example, traced the influence of both the modern and Russian traditions of writing fiction on the novelist by epitomizing striking and enduring affinities with Dostoevsky, James Joyce, Gustave Flaubert, André Gide, Kafka, and the British Victorian novel in general. Harold Bloom overemphasized the romantic elements in the Bellovian texts. He admitted that the British Romantic poets had a profound influence on the author's moral ideals. Andrew Marino and Peter Carl Surace have undertaken academic studies on the novelist's position within the intellectual literary scene in the United States. Accordingly, comparative studies have been conducted on the affinities and differences between Bellow, on the one hand, and other authors, such as Philip Roth, Norman Mailer, and Bernard Malamud. One significant conclusion that can be drawn from their findings is that all these authors discussed in their works the same themes as: the Holocaust, femininity, the image of the intellectual in the modern age, history, exile, madness, and wisdom Bellow's peculiarity stems from a) his being influenced by this intellectual context, b) his ceaseless attempts 'to innovate and subvert the ordinary strategies of writing both stylistically and semantically.' Nevertheless, this high intellectual reputation could not hide the novelist's inconsistent instances and major weaknesses. First, although he legislated for moral laws, he paradoxically remained entrapped in the same habits of thoughts he wanted to abandon. His moral theories of happiness, justice, faith and humanism are utopian and paradoxical. Second, the literary and intellectual scene in the US had a profound influence on him, causing him to narrow his focus to certain themes and issues. Ultimately, regarding the author's 'personal ends,' one can safely admit that his novels tell personal stories or incorporate autobiographical elements of his life, rather than depicting human cases in general. As a result, one can deduce that although the literary and intellectual contexts in the US have largely affected the author's imagination, yet, as shall be demonstrated in the forthcoming parts of this paper, it also reinforces the notion of inconsistencies in his fictional world either by the hegemonic traces that have highly governed his focus or hiding certain insights from him.

Let us now pause for a moment and reflect on another fundamental inconsistency, which is Bellow's 'skillful misrecognition' of specific intellectual figures and theories. In fact, one can admittedly assume that the author has extensively referred to the theories of morality, the assumptions of psychoanalysis, the premises of Marxism, and the methods of anthropology and structuralism, which demands being aware of philosophers like Hegel, Marx, and Barthes. Nevertheless, this could not conceal the fact that the author was not fully aware of the significant intellectual debate between poststructuralism and post-poststructuralism. He misread or "refused to read" in his fictional world the intellectual 'scandals' between the French and the German philosophers, the conflict between the French universities on the one hand and the British and North American universities on the other hand, the theories of the death of theory and the theory of the rise of cultural studies in its various forms entitled the renewed focus on the political, the concrete, and the culturally specific, in comparison with which theory can be seen as elitist, patriarchal, universalizing and Eurocentric. The novelist did not elaborate on the crucial role of the French theorists in fixing the quality of knowledge in the world. He did not read Lyotard's postmodern condition of knowledge, Lévinas's theories on stories and after stories, Althusser's views on reading and self-reading, and Foucault's reflections on the crisis of knowledge. The period during which the novelist was active forms a significant part of his life, almost half of it, and yet he did not intend to relate his writings to these theories. Concerned with publishing his novels, Bellow pays no attention to the rapid changes that were taking place in literary

criticism and philosophy at the time he was writing. In short, when writing his novels, he was re-producing the same inconsistencies and weaknesses of the Enlightenment anew.

More strikingly, Saul Bellow sought to develop a comprehensive theory of madness and subversion/deconstruction without referencing philosophers and intellectuals such as Derrida and Foucault. Without paying careful attention to literature, Bellow could not notice Derrida's revisionist readings on the relationship between the metaphoricity of literature and the logic of philosophy, on the one hand, and the limits of metaphysical/logocentric and Enlightenment norms of thought, on the other. When Derrida addresses the science of writing and interpretation (Derrida, 1976, p. 33), the overlap between discourses (namely the literary and the philosophical) (Derrida, 1972; 2000 pp. 24, 26), and the possibility of the regeneration and the deconstruction of the meaning out of the multiperspectivist positions of the reader, the novelist was concentrating all his efforts on re-writing and subverting the Enlightenment. One logical result is that, although the two figures share the same strategy of deconstruction, they lack a solid intellectual foundation on which to meet. Additionally, one can mention the author's neglect of Foucault's insights on madness and sanity. In this, when Foucault demonstrates a careful awareness of the history of madness and wisdom by adopting a genealogical method and archaeological design, Bellow was highly concerned with the madness of intellectuals, tracing thereby scrupulous affinities with Socrates in particular and Metaphysics in general. The author could not take the Foucauldian project of madness further simply because the metaphysical habits of thought entrapped him. More interestingly, he was unable to see the relationship between his theory of the madness of the intellect and the crisis of knowledge, which represented a significant intellectual debate between poststructuralist scholars. Accordingly, the author could not explore and exploit Deleuze's insights concerning the multiplicity of different knowledge(s) and culture(s) since his thoughts were 'largely dominated by hegemonic Jewish assumptions.' To this, he did not mention in his late writings de Man's allegories of reading, Hutcheon's politics of representations, Bauman's ethics of postmodernism, Habermas's insights on the unfinished project of modernity, Althusser's after hope, Lévinas's after ethics and so on. In short, the novelist wrote his novels and let them in the hands of his readers without paying much attention to what was happening around him.

One more inconsistency is the novelist's blindness to the insights of the French women philosophers while addressing the tragedy of the subject, moral anxiety, human life, and human nature. Bellow's fictional world is inhabited by female heroes who endlessly seek to assert their femininity. Nevertheless, what the novelist was blind to was that he could not investigate these gestures of questioning and the deconstruction of the subject within the context of French intellectual feminist philosophy. He depicted simple relationships between men and women, heroes and heroines, husbands and wives, victims and victimizers without relating this to Françoise Collin's notes on the tragedy of the feminine subject. 'Being imprisoned within the metaphysical habits of thinking,' he could not enrich his fictional imagination with what Collin would call the praxis of difference, feminism, and the post-metaphysical attempts of emancipation, the glorification of women (Collin, 2004, pp. 7-24). The novelist forgets to mention and exploit the tragic intellectual conflicts between femininity and masculinity, womanhood and manhood, power and otherness. Monique Canto-Sperber's careful assessment of the myth of modernity and the ill-treatment of individualism could not find their way into his novels (Sperber, 2004, p. 24-39). Sylviane Aagcinski's critique of egocentrism and logocentrism, Luce Irigaray's questioning of the problem of otherness (either woman or man), and Natalie Depraz's investigation to women imagination and passivity in relationship with Husserl's phenomenology and Kant's morality could not help the novelist sketch the border lines between metaphysics and the Enlightenment on the one hand and feminism, post-Enlightenment or post-theory on the other hand. The point behind this, I see, is that while the author dealt with classical theories carefully, he paradoxically neglected the other contemporary theories of texts and post-morality. In doing so, he failed to discover the deep and organic ties between them. He was unable to exploit Cixous's notions of alterity and otherness fully, Kristeva's sharp criticism of universality and its disastrous effects, and, in short, he could not understand the feminine subject from ethical, philosophical, psychoanalytic, rational, scientific, political, and even juridical perspectives. On this, one can only wonder whether he understood metaphysics and the Enlightenment or not! Acknowledging Habermas's postulates on 'the unfinished project of modernity,' one can also radically suspect Bellow's knowledge about his age.

I may be accused of introducing thereby subjective criticism, and my response about this accusation would be in three ways:

- a) Although the author was aware of some of the theories and seriously strived to exploit their insights, he remained blind to some others. In this way, one cannot judge the novelist for being ignorant of the insights of his age. One cannot also praise him for being the philosopher of this age. Therefore, it is upon this logic that one can develop a possible and objective criticism.
- b) One cannot by any means ignore the hegemonic assumptions that influenced the author's fictional world. One logical result is that addressing them carefully would help us gain a better understanding of his subversive strategies. Another result is that it may save us from criticism.
- c) Engaging in serious cultural criticism requires a skeptical and subversive approach that examines the details. The point is that the novelist's strategies of deconstruction should not escape the act of criticism itself.

PREMISES

My search for both Bellow's strategies of subversion/deconstruction and the intellectual, theoretical, and philosophical context that affected the author's 'growth of mind' has led me to identify some of the main and strikingly shared features in his fictional world. At this point, it would seem advisable to argue that Bellow's early writings are largely regarded as straightforward novels that explore ordinary themes such as peace, war, love, happiness, social relationships, and faithfulness. Critics like Malcolm Bradbury, Harold Bloom, John Jacob Clayton, Gloria L. Cronin, Michael Glenday, and Irving Malin enumerate the fundamental characteristics that qualify Bellow's early writings in the following way:

- a) Reason, faith, freedom, progress, unity, harmony, morality, humanism.
- b) The project is usually identified through rationality and universality, which Lyotard dubbed metanarratives.
- c) Will, authority, and the courage to use one's own understanding and 'wisdom'.
- d) modern thought, rooted in the context of the Enlightenment, has taken a number of wrong turns in its endeavors to correct the shortcomings of the Enlightenment.
- e) The ongoing nature of the Enlightenment. In other words, the project of modernity is still unfinished and requires completion.

These insights are highly hinged on a simplistic reading of the novelist's fictional world. One blind spot missed by these critics is that they could not re-read the author in the light of the rapidly changing theories of literary criticism and philosophy. Accordingly, it is for this reason that they limited the scope of their research to thematic and structural and thematic patterns without paying much attention to the intellectual context of the age.

Nevertheless, the subversive and deconstructive nature of the author's writings both at the levels of discourse (the overlap between discourses [...]) and theme (the investigation of the themes of madness as wisdom, morality as amorality [...]) entails the necessity of re-evaluating my views in the light of the contemporary insights of theory. Considering all this, critics have identified the features that reveal the novelist's self-consciousness and mental growth in an unfinished project of maturity and enlightenment. Their findings can be read as follows:

- Amorality, skepticism, disorder
- Madness, absurdity, illusion
- Fear, intellectual instability, theory wars, silence
- Marginality, reality, purposelessness
- Deconstruction, subversion, restlessness, vacuum

These results, I acknowledge, were introduced and then quickly revised twice. Building on the richness of the texts and their potential for interpretation from different and even opposing perspectives, critics take their views to the extreme by addressing concepts such as after- knowledge, politics, religion, ethics, and representation. Signaling never-ending gestures of re- interpretation and understanding, the term 'after' becomes a keyword in developing this review:

- a") 'After knowledge': the crisis of knowledge
- b") After hope: the crisis of hope
- c") After identity: Bellow's life without stories
- d") After politics: the odyssey of exile and the imaginary homelands
- e") The Holocaust: after history
- f") Memory: after memory, madness and subversion

One fundamental caveat that needs to be taken seriously is that during this long period of writing, which was previously mentioned as a process of maturity, the author has been remarkably influenced by many factors:

- a) Twentieth-century historical political context.
- b) The ideology of Jewishness, including the concepts of exile, Holocaust, identity, otherness, and sacrifice.
- c) The 'philosophical and the theoretical trends of thought to which he was contemporaneous.'
- d) The autobiographical elements of his life and his 'ceaseless strife' to envision a better, if not a utopian, view of life.

e) and, eventually, his mind's subversive and deconstructive nature. Nevertheless, a few questions crop up to our minds: to what extent did the theories of his age influence the author? Did he exploit them appropriately in his writings? Considering this multiperspectivist context, could it be argued that two logical results out of these never-ending sets of theories are inconsistent and lack a logical relationship between the concepts discussed? Can we safely say that the hegemony of certain ideological stances legitimates the possibility of critically revising the novelist's mind and world? Overall, Bellow's fiction stands at the crossroads of intellectual ambition and ideological contradiction, simultaneously striving for coherence while embracing fragmentation. Though deeply engaged with philosophical and literary traditions, his narratives often expose the limitations of his own critical approach, making his work a fertile ground for deconstructive analysis.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Bellow's writings serve as a testament to the complexities of modern intellectual thought, revealing the tensions between philosophical explorations and narrative contradictions. However, my response to these interrogations would be positive. My point is that the writer has shown moments of inconsistencies and sometimes a lack of logic in the growth of his mind. The simplistic reading of the Enlightenment, the hazy and even too general investigation of the postmodern and the after-postmodern norms of thinking, the blindness to the insights of social theory, the theories of philosophy and criticism, and the ideological stances legitimate the gesture of establishing a critical reading to the author's madness and strategies of subversion.

The author's failure to understand the Enlightenment as 'an unfinished project' to cite Habermas or to find out the link between the different historical and intellectual moments (modernity, modernism, postmodernity, and after postmodernity) deepens the idea of inconsistency in the novelist's fictional world, and interestingly reinforces the postulate that Bellow's deconstruction cannot escape the act of criticism itself. The interplay of subversion and affirmation in his fiction suggests that while he challenges certain philosophical doctrines, he simultaneously upholds others in ways that may be at odds with his deconstructive approach.

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